

A Bibliography of Critical Responses to Racial Hereditarian Research

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Since 2012, over 350 journal articles and books claim that folk racial classifications are biologically meaningful categories and that racial differences in intelligence test scores, educational attainment, income, and crime partly or even primarily originate from genetic differences between those races. Some psychologists claim that the differences between White Europeans and Black Africans or African Americans are highly resistant to change, and result from evolved differences in brain size, testosterone, and reproductive strategies produced by natural selection. We refer to this body of work as “racial hereditarian research” or RHR and the authors as “RHR psychologists.”

This bibliography lists articles, chapters, and books which critique RHR psychology appearing since 1985. The starting year of 1985 was chosen as the year of Philippe Rushton’s first statement of his theory of racial differences in a psychology journal:

Rushton, J. P. (1985). Differential K theory: The sociobiology of individual and group differences. *Personality and Individual Differences* 6, 441-452.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869\(85\)90137-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0191-8869(85)90137-0)

Section 1 lists works that respond directly to RHR. This section should show that RHR is not taboo, but is openly debated, and rejected, by mainstream psychology, genetics, evolutionary biology, and biological anthropology. Section 2 lists works, primarily but not exclusively from evolutionary biology, human and medical genetics, and biological anthropology that underscores how those fields conceptualize race and biology, testing adaptive hypotheses, and using Genome-Wide Association Studies and polygenic scores. It demonstrates that the fundamental ideas of RHR are roundly rejected within those sciences. At times a particular article was difficult to place definitely in one section or another, consequently readers should consult both sections in their work.

This bibliography should not be considered exhaustive, and we apologize to authors whose work has been omitted.

Section 1: Direct Responses to Racial Hereditarian Research since 1985.

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Section 2: Additional critiques

Including materials from:

- Cautions about improper uses of polygenic scores and GWAS.
- Scientific statements and literature on the ethical obligations of scientists studying human variation.
- Criticisms of the use of “race,” especially “continental races,” or folk races as categories in the anthropological, biological and medical sciences.
- Endorsements from the anthropological, biological and medical sciences that “race” is a socially constructed category, not a biological entity.
- Criticisms of conflating Self Identified Race and Ethnicity (SIRE) with genetic ancestry.
- Works that recognize the reality of systemic racism as a cause of biological and medical problems.

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